

Photonics4All app

“Photonics is the Science and technology of generating, controlling, and detecting Light.”

Download our amazing App to learn more about Photonics!

NOW ONLINE ON

<http://photonics4all-app.eu/> !

The App consists of 5 modules. These modules include games and quizzes which makes our **App fun and interesting**. Test our App yourself! You can download it on GooglePlay Store.

Scan the QR code

More at www.photonics4all.eu/

Photonics4All
Discover the Power of Light

GET IT ON

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